

Computational analysis techniques provide significant insights into Citizen Science

The European CS Track project recently published a detailed report describing how computational analysis techniques can be used to help us better understand the growing Citizen Science phenomenon. Insights and evidence provided through this work are combined with empirical-interpretative approaches originating from social studies practices to create guidance and recommendations aimed at a variety of stakeholders including policy-makers.

The recently published report entitled “**Specification of Web-based Analytics Methods and Tools**” specifies the CS Track approach in terms of the selection and description of pertinent methods and their relevance in the citizen science context. The report illustrates part of the approach with a sample application of network analysis techniques applied to a Zooniverse case. The report also explains the intended usage of the methodology.

The project team plan to apply Web-based Analytics Methods and Tools at three different levels; **Macro** with a wide scope on web and social media as data sources, **Meso** where groups of projects from the CS Track database are analysed and compared in a uniform way and **Micro**, where individual projects are examined using additional specific information sources such as project forums and wikis. These levels are elaborated in the following table:

Level	Tools/Methods	Scope	Purpose (example)
Macro	Harvesting of Twitter data, network analyses, text mining	Open collections of projects or initiatives beyond the CS Track database	Identification of trends, “public outreach”, “popularity”.
Meso	Information extraction from homogeneously formatted datasets	Collections of projects in the CS Track database	Identification of research areas, relation to SDGs
Micro	Harvesting and analysis of project-specific web resources such as forum or wiki data	Small samples selected from the CS Track database using specific criteria	Participation profiles and distribution of roles

Download the full report [here](#).

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